

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 0.98

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF CUSTOMER SHOPPING BEHAVIOUR IN RETAIL STORE

Irshad Ahmad*

Assistant Professor,
Al-Falah University, Faridabad, Haryana

Dr. Keshav Gupta**

Satyawati College (Evening),
Delhi University, Delhi, India

ABSTRACT

Retail is at present the flourishing sector of the Indian economy. Availability of quality, retail space, wider availability of products and brand communication are some of the factors that are driving the retail in India. Organized retail sector has emerged within the retail industry and it gave speedy phase to Indian retail sector. This study examines the consumer buying behaviour in shopping mall. The broad objective of the study is to understand consumer behavior towards organized and unorganized retail stores and to find out the consumers satisfaction level from organized retail stores as well as unorganized retail stores.

Key words: unorganized retail, Organised, Consumer

INTRODUCTION:

The Indian retail industry is divided into two **sectors:** organized and unorganized. The Indian retail industry is now beginning to evolve transformation that has swept other large economies. The concept retail, which includes the shopkeeper to customer interaction, has taken many forms and dimensions, from the traditional retail outlet and street local market shops to upscale multi brand outlets, especially stores or departmental stores. Hence, focusing on two aspects of retail marketing, i.e., store retailing and non-store retailing. Store Retailing as the departmental store, which is a store or multi brand outlet, offering an array of products in various categories under one roof, trying to cater to not one or two but many segments of the society and Non store retailing as the direct selling, direct marketing, automatic vending. The organized retail food and grocery stores make constant efforts to induce customers to visit the store by discount offers. Most of these stores believe in creating not just a marketing activity with its customers, but rather favor relationship building with him so as to convert first time customers into a client. They provide better parking facilities to customers and the facility to examine the product. They also offer a wide range of payment options to customers. India is currently the twelfth largest consumer market in the world. According to a study by McKinsey Global Institute, India is likely to join the premier league of the world's consumer markets by 2025 improving its position to the fifth.

ORGANIZED VS. UNORGANIZED SECTOR

The Organised retailing refers to the trading activities undertaken by licensed retailers that is those who registered themselves for sales tax, income tax, etc. These include the corporate – backed hypermarkets and retail chains and also the privately owned large businesses. Indian retail is dominated by a large number of small retailers consisting of the local kirana shops, owner-manned general stores, chemists, footwear shops, apparel shops, paan and beedi shops, hand-cart hawkers, pavement vendors, etc. which together make up the so-called “unorganized retail” or traditional retail. Organized retailing is based on the principle of unity and unorganized retailing is based on the principle of singularity. Both organized and unorganized retailing is found in most of the countries throughout the world. India and China are strong examples of countries in which unorganized retailing dominated their markets. Today these countries have a growing economy because of the influx of organized retailers into their markets. The last 3-4 years have witnessed the entry of a number of organized retailers, opening stores in various modern formats in metros and other important cities. The growth in organized retailing in recent years can also be gauged by the rise of shopping malls as well as the rising number of modern retail formats.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Purohit and Kavita according to their studies that the traditional retailers are not very much clear about the consequences of the modern retailing the traditional retailers are neutral or undecided, modern retailing will cut the profit margin of the traditional retailers; the modern retailing will lead healthy competition in the market, modern retailing will reduce the sales volume of the traditional retailers and traditional retailers should improve customer care services in the era of modern retailing.

Shaoni Shabnam: It is important to highlight that in organized retail, the status of employment is much better than that in unorganized retail. Hence it is definitely desirable that more and more labor gets absorbed in this sector of retail. In the current context, the labor employed in unorganized retail stands unfit for finding employment in organized retail. If appropriate training and skills could be imparted to them, it is possibly feasible to offer better forms of employment to them in the organized retail sector. The status of employment is much better than that in unorganized retail.

Meeta Punjabi: According to their study they suggest that the development efforts in this area

are based on three grounds: First, farmers associated with the modern value chains earn higher returns than selling to the traditional markets. Second, the modern supply chains have specific quality requirements which are easier to meet by the large and medium farmers and the small farmers tend to get left out of these markets. Third, there are several successful examples of linking small farmers to these modern value chains with effort from government agencies, NGOs and development agencies. This knowledge presents strong grounds for a closer look at the emerging sector in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sampling:

Obtaining a sample is necessary, since collecting data from the entire population (a census) is virtually impossible. The key to sampling is to achieve representativeness of the population. The two approaches to sampling are probability and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling is used more commonly where issues of generalizability and/or drawing statistical conclusions are involved (Hair et al., 2003). Non-probability samples, on the other hand, are chosen during the exploratory phases and during pretesting of survey questionnaires. Hair et al. (2003) poses three principal questions for determining the course of the research process: (I) whether a sample or census should be used, (II) in the case of sampling, which sampling approach to use, and (III) how large the sample should be.

In quantitative research, the primary goal is to obtain a representative sample. The researcher's aim is to collect a small unit of cases from a large population, in which a smaller group is representative of a larger group of the population, and the researcher can produce accurate generalizations about the larger group (Neuman, 2003).

SAMPLE AND DATA COLLECTION:

With respect to the sampling, a convenience and snow ball sampling was utilized to survey of 540 respondents from different occupations. A total of 1200 self-administered questionnaire forms were e-mailed and personally given to respondents using simple random sampling. Out of 1200, only 850 questionnaires were received back. But only 540 questionnaire forms were found correctly filled and were used for data analysis.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

The research design was related to organised retailing in India. The present research focused on the shopping motives and shopping activities, shopping Mall image, various promotional activities of mall as a source of attraction for customers, and on the experience and expectations of the customers from organised retailers. The present research was explorative in nature because the data that was already available but mainly regarding the foreign markets. This study intended to conduct the research in the domestic market, specifically in Delhi and NCR. Therefore data was collected from this region only. Primary data for this study was collected by means of a survey conducted in Delhi & NCR in India from Jan-July-2013. Some statistical tools like Chi square, Cronbach's Alpha, exploratory factor analysis, and Regression Analysis were conducted in order to validate the measurement properties of the constructs identified in the exploratory factor analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Different statistical methods can be used to make sense of collected data sets. According to Hair et al. (2007), two steps are involved in quantitative data analyses: 1) descriptive statistics to obtain a descriptive overview of data in hand, and 2) using statistical tests for hypothesis testing. For this study, we have conducted the following statistical analysis to make sense of the data.

Descriptive statistics

In order to get a descriptive overview of the data, descriptive statistics is used, and this statistical analysis summarizes the large set of data through a limited number of meaningful statistical indicators. Each variable is studied separately to compare average scores of variables among the different groups of respondents (Janssens et al., 2008). Usually, descriptive statistics contain three types of indicators: frequency distribution, central tendency measures, and dispersion measures.

Analysis of demographic profile of the Respondents

There were total 540 completed responses, out of which 40.74 % were female and the remaining 59.26% were male respondents. The age profile of the respondents. 35.4% of respondents are within the range of 31-40 years, 22.0% in the 41-50 years range, 15.56% are in 51-60 years range, 19.26% 708% is less than 30 years old and 19.30% are above 60 years old at the time the survey is conducted. A majority (57.4%) of the respondents represent the age range of 31-50.

The respondents’ highest level of education has also been examined. As presented in Figure 18.15% of the respondents have Under Graduate education. 37.78% of the respondents have graduate degrees, 27.96% of the respondents have postgraduate qualifications, and 16.11% of the respondents have vocational training qualifications.

How often do you visit Malls?

Table and graph below show that a major percent (37.6%) of respondents visits Mall on weekends followed by 26.9% of respondents who visit Mall fortnightly. While 17.6% of respondents visit Mall on monthly basis and 9.6% of respondents visit mall on festive occasions. The remaining 8.3% of respondents visit mall as and when required.

Table: Frequency of visiting Mall:

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Once in a month	95	17.6	17.6	17.6
	Fortnightly	145	26.9	26.9	44.4
	Week ends	203	37.6	37.6	82.0
	Festive occasion	52	9.6	9.6	91.7
	As and when required	45	8.3	8.3	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Figure: Frequency of visiting Mall

Q. You Visit Mall with whom?

From the table, 58.3% of respondents visit mall on your own followed by 31.7% of

Table: You visit Mall with

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	On your own	315	58.3	58.3	58.3
	Along with your peers	171	31.7	31.7	90.0
	Along with your family members	54	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

respondents who visit mall along with their peers and friends. There are only 10% of respondents who visit mall along with their family members. It shows that generally people like to visit mall either alone or with their friend and peers.

Figure: You visit Mall with

Average Time spent in Mall during a visit:

Generally a major part (49.6%) of the respondents spend 2-3 hrs in a shopping mall during their visit followed by 26.3% of the respondents who spend 1-2 hrs in a shopping mall during their visit. There are only 9.4% of the respondents who spend less than one hour and 14.6% of the respondents who spend more than 3 hours hrs in a shopping mall during their visit.

Table: Time spent in Mall

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 1 hour	51	9.4	9.4	9.4
	1 – 2 hrs	142	26.3	26.3	35.7
	2-3 hrs	268	49.6	49.6	85.4
	More than 3 hrs	79	14.6	14.6	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Figure:Time spent in Mall

Day To Day Required Articles Purchased From Malls:

Table and Figure below show that there are 68.7% of respondents who like to purchase their day to day required items from mall while 31.3% of respondents who like to purchase their day to day required items from somewhere else. It shows that people do not prefer to go to mall if the same item is available at nearby place or if they do not have time to visit mall immediately.

Table: Day To Day Required Articles Purchased From Malls

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	371	68.7	68.7	68.7
	No	169	31.3	31.3	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Figure :Day To Day Required Articles Purchased From Malls

What Percent of Items do you Purchase From Malls?

From the table and graph below, it is clear that there are almost 56% of respondents who purchase 26 – 80% of total items from shopping mall while there are only 11.1% of respondents who purchase 81-100% of total items from shopping mall. On the other hand, only 11.7% of respondents purchase less than 10% of total items and 21.1% of respondents who purchase 11-25% of total items from shopping mall.

Table:Percent of items purchase from Malls

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	>10%	63	11.7	11.7	11.7
	11-25%	114	21.1	21.1	32.8
	26-50%	161	29.8	29.8	62.6
	51-80%	142	26.3	26.3	88.9
	81-100%	60	11.1	11.1	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Figure: Percent of items purchase from Malls

Where else do you purchase required items except Mall?

Description shows that people do not buy 100% of total items required from mall. They also purchase them from some alternate places.

Table: Place Of Purchase Except Mall

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Kirana shop	234	43.3	43.3	43.3
	Street vender	141	26.1	26.1	69.4
	Super Market	78	14.4	14.4	83.9
	Departmental store	61	11.3	11.3	95.2
	Tele- venders	26	4.8	4.8	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Figure: Place Of Purchase Except Mall:

There are 43.3% of respondents who generally buy their day to day required items from kirana shop followed by 26.1% of respondents who prefer to buy it from street vendors. While 14.4% of respondents visit Super market and 11.3% of respondents visit departmental store to purchase their daily required items. There are only 4.8% of respondents who adopt tele- vendors as alternative medium of purchase of daily required items.

From which source you get relevant information about the malls?

Table and graph below show that 66.9% of the respondents get the relevant information about the malls through advertisement followed by 26.1% of the respondents getting relevant information from Peers and acquaintances. There are only 7% of the respondents who get the information from sales persons about the malls.

Table: Source of Relevant Information about The Malls

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Advertisement	361	66.9	66.9	66.9
	Peers and acquaintances	141	26.1	26.1	93.0
	Sales persons	38	7.0	7.0	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Figure: Source of Relevant Information about The Malls

State the Advertising Medium Which Entices the Buyers To Visit Malls.

The table shows that on an average 93.2% of customers consider news paper as the most entices advertising medium of advertisement followed by Ad on wheels by 90% of the customers. Mall’s own advertising by 87.8% of the customers , Radio (FM) by 87% of the customers and television by 86.7% of the customers as the 4th, 5th and 6th place followed by Billboard/Hoarding by 86.6% of the customers as the 7th most entices medium of advertisement .

Table: Different Advertising medium

Advertising Medium	Most Important		Important		Moderately Important		Unimportant		Most Unimportant	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Television	81	15.0	169	31.3	218	40.4	33	6.1	39	7.2
News paper	129	23.9	231	42.8	143	26.5	25	4.6	12	2.2
Magazine	31	5.7	102	18.9	221	40.9	147	27.2	39	7.2
Radio (FM)	139	25.7	146	27.0	185	34.3	49	9.1	21	3.9
Billboard/Hoarding	79	14.6	213	39.4	176	32.6	41	7.6	31	5.7
Brochure / Pamphlets	51	9.4	119	22.0	234	43.3	109	20.2	27	5.0
Wall-writing	43	7.96	128	23.7	203	37.5	112	20.7	54	10
Ad on wheels	103	19.1	181	33.5	202	37.4	33	6.1	21	3.9
Mall’s own advertising	58	10.7	131	24.3	285	52.8	37	6.9	29	5.4

Brochure / Pamphlets are considered as an important medium of advertisement by 74.7% of the people and Wall-writing by 69.16% of the customers. While magazine as an advertisement medium is considered important by 65.5% of the customers.

The analysis has shown that news paper and Ad on wheels are the most entices advertising medium having influence on customers’ attitude.

Q. How would you state your overall experience with various promotional activities of mall?

Table and graph show that almost 63.3% of respondents have over all positive experience with various promotional activities of shopping malls. There are only 15% and 7.2% of the

respondents who have negative and partially negative experience respectively with various promotional activities of shopping malls.

Table: Overall Experience With Various Promotional Activities Of Mall

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Positive	181	33.5	33.5	33.5
	Partially Positive	161	29.8	29.8	63.3
	Neutral	78	14.4	14.4	77.8
	Partially Negative	39	7.2	7.2	85.0
	Negative	81	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

The table & graph below show that 33.5% of the customers have positive experience followed by 63.3% of the customers have partial positive experience with various promotional activities of mall. It shows that the various promotional activities of mall are able to meet the minimum expectation of the customers. While 14.4% of the customers are not in a position to express their level of satisfaction with various promotional activities of mall. On the other hand, 15.005 of the customers had negative experience with various promotional activities of mall followed by 7.2% of the customers with partially negative experience. It shows that various promotional activities of mall are not able to meet the expectation of all the customers. It caters the need of some specific clusters or segments.

Figure: Overall Experience With Various Promotional Activities Of Mall

Q. What more do you expect to be provided at this Mall?

Table: What more to be provided at the Mall

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	More products	119	22.0	22.0	22.0
	Additional brands	50	9.3	9.3	31.3
	Enhanced services	89	16.5	16.5	47.8
	Genuine Discounts	151	28.0	28.0	75.7
	Sales promotional scheme	131	24.3	24.3	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.18 and graph 4.16 show that customers (28%) are looking for Genuine Discounts followed by 24% and 22% of the respondents preferring Sales promotional schemes and variety of the products respectively. While 16.5% of the respondents want more enhanced services in the mall and 9.3% of respondents are in search of Additional brands in the shopping mall.

Figure:What more to be provided at the Mall

Q. What additional single facility you would like to have in this shopping mall?

The table and graph below show that a major portion of the respondents (62.8%) is desirous to have entertainment facilities like Pubs followed by 22.4% of the respondents for casinos in shopping Malls. Games and Health Club are not in demand in shopping Malls as only 9.4% and 5.45 of the respondents are looking for health and games facilities respectively in the shopping malls.

Table: Additional single facility to have in the shopping mall

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Health Club	51	9.4	9.4	9.4
	Pubs	339	62.8	62.8	72.2
	Casinos	121	22.4	22.4	94.6
	Games	29	5.4	5.4	100.0
	Total	540	100.0	100.0	

Figure: Additional single facility to have in the shopping mall

LIMITATIONS & FUTURE RESEARCH

The study has been conducted in Delhi/NCR, India. The results of the same, if conducted in other part of the county may vary. Shopping motivation in this study captures the general tendency of respondents towards the act of shopping. It is likely that individuals display different shopping motivations on varying occasions. While this study identified several shopping motivations Indian consumers go for shopping, it may have missed others. These motivations will need to be measured empirically in future research.

Regarding questionnaire distribution, Buyers and sellers were randomly selected near shopping Malls in Delhi/NCR , this survey questionnaire would not perfectly representative for the entire Indian buyers and sellers population.

This study opens doors to many research ideas and investigations. Ethnographic research, as proven useful here, can be further utilized in order to gain deeper insights into the types of stores visited by shoppers inside shopping malls, as the typology in this study was based on shopping motives and shopping activities related to each motive regardless of the stores visited at the mall. Focusing on the store as a unit of analysis can potentially enhance the current findings and mall-shopper typologies in general. Furthermore, a closer investigation of the relationship between occasions or specific times of the year and types of shoppers visiting the mall and the types of activities performed can also provide deeper insights to the reasons behind visiting malls and why malls are particularly crowded or overwhelmed on specific occasions such as Eid (a Muslim Feast), Christmas, and Easter, especially in this part of the world where the mall is regarded as a significant outing for leisure, household shopping, and entertainment.

CONCLUSION

The growth in the Indian organized retail market is mainly due to the change in the consumer's behavior. This change has come in the consumer due to increased income, changing, lifestyles, and patterns of demography which are favorable. Now the consumer wants to shop at a place where he can get food, entertainment, and shopping all under one roof. This has given Indian organized retail market a major boost.

In India it is quite doubtful that the organized retail will be ever able to overcome the unorganized retail completely. The values culture and beliefs of the customers prompt them to go the same retail shop where they can get the product required, at low price and with least

waiting time for billing. No matter how lucrative is this sector and how bright is the market; the organized sector in retailing has to go a long way to understand the customer requirement.

REFERENCES:

Agrwal Vaishli and Sanjay Mishra (2008), “Role of Retailers in Reducing Inventory And Improving Customer Satisfaction: An Empirical Study Of Consumer Durables”, Indian Journal of Marketing, pp. 36-43.

Baseer Amatual and G Laxmi Prabha (2007), “Prospects and Problems of Indian Retailing”, Indian Journal of Marketing, pp. 26-28.

Bhatnagar Gitanjali (2004), “Retail Revolution”, Indian Journal of Marketing, pp. 13-17.

Dave Sumita, Shikha Sondhi and Saket Ranjan Praveer (2008), “Effectiveness of ETailing in the era of Techno Revolution in retailing With Respect to Vending Machines”, Journal of Marketing and Communication, Vol. 4, pp. 71-79.

Dixon T J (2005), “The Role of Retailing in Urban Regeneration, Local Economy, Vol. 20, No. 2, pp. 168-182.

Gupta C P (2008), “Rajeev Agarwal and Madhuli casinha, Organised Retailing and its Effect on Consumer Buying Behavior with Special Reference to Agra City”, Journal of Marketing and Communication, pp. 80-88.

Joseph Mathew, Nirupama Soundararajan, Manisha Gupta and Sanghamitra Sahu (2008), Impact of Organised Retailing on Unorganised Sector Working Paper ICRIER, p. 222.

Venkateshwarlu H and Ranjani C V (2007), “Small Vs Mall”, Indian Journal of Marketing, pp. 29-33.